

CLT METHOD TO TEACH ESP COURSE FOR THE STUDENTS OF THE TAXATION FIELD

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Abstract. ESP (English for Specific Purposes) is special English classes for students who are studying in other spheres. As English is an international language, it turned into a means of globalization. Therefore, English is being taught as a main subject in all education centers. However, teaching ESP is not easy job, it differs from teaching General English. It requires professional teachers, special syllabus, books and others. The most important thing in teaching ESP is identifying students' needs and organizing the lesson based on the students' needs. Choosing appropriate methods and approaches is also essential. It is beneficial to integrate various technological devices during the lesson as it helps the students to learn better. Taxation is one of the spheres in which the students are learning English language as one of their main subjects.

Key words: approach, method, data analysis, taxation sphere, skill, CLT, integration, implement, policy, strategy

ESP (English for Specific Purposes) became a distinct field of English teaching coming to 1960s. The development of "the science and technology" caused the English to be an international language around the world and it started to be implemented in other spheres such as business, tourism, data analysis, health and others; then they started to learn their spheres in English. ESP course achieved the popularity around the world as it improved the international relationships and caused the development.

ESP course for students in taxation sphere is new enhancement in this field. As the ESP course should be based on the students' needs, needs analysis is suggested to organize among the students who study or work in this sphere (Dudley-Evans, 1998). Furthermore, Lamri (2016) remarks the importance of correlation between "the needs, goals and motivation of the learners", learners' and teachers' attitudes towards learning and teaching. Therefore, needs analysis is strongly suggested. According to the result of the needs analysis, the materials are chosen and implemented in the process. Needs analysis is the core of ESP teaching as it is clarified that what kind of language skills are needed during the ESP course for the students. And the needed skills are more emphasized in the course. Survey and interview are the best methods to utilize for needs analysis process. To have ESP course, students should have enough language proficiency level at least B1. Therefore, the learners' language proficiency level should be

identified with the help of proficiency tests and they are selected based on their language proficiency level. However, according to Woodrow (2018) the learners' proficiency level can be "beginner". In this kind of situations, firstly, the learners' language proficiency level should be improved in the first stages of the course and then they should be introduced with the ESP course materials. This is more effective way of teaching ESP.

Teachers who teach the ESP course in this field can have lessons without any stages like: warm-up, pre-, while and post parts. Instead, they can continue from the part which they left in the previous lesson according to the syllabus which they prepared specifically for this intended course. The most difficult part is to prepare syllabus for the ESP course as the sphere is a bit complicated for the teachers. There are little textbooks specially written for the students in taxation so the teachers are required to create the materials by themselves or to find the textbooks related to the sphere. Teachers can create some vocabulary lists by having research from different resources as vocabulary is the most necessary part of teaching and learning. Finding specific textbooks for only taxation is so demanding and difficult, therefore, the textbooks related to the accounting, business, finance are the best options to be chosen. They are more relevant to this sphere. As vocabulary and Grammar are the basic parts of language acquisition process, before starting the ESP course, students' language proficiency level should be checked and if it is needed the course should be started with teaching vocabulary and grammar or they should be implemented during the whole course. Teachers who teach the ESP course for the students in taxation field should be "great motivator" as "most of ESP students are less fond of studying English and most of them claim that English is not important because it is beyond their field and thus is useless, ignoring the fact that English is very crucial for them to support their competence in the future" (Fatmawati, S. A. Gani & I. A. Samad). The best way to motivate them is to implement different kind of digital devices, videos, techniques, authentic materials, strategies to the classes.

The intention should be to improve the students' communicative abilities since the taxation field requires more communication and exchanging of information with each other. To develop international relationships with the most developed countries in terms of tax and taxation and to be able understand different information about taxation policy of developed countries around the world, the representatives of the field should have enough communicative skills. However, other skills: listening, writing and reading are also emphasized.

ESP course should be in learner-centered mode as learner-centered approach in

teaching gives students more chance to participate actively during the lesson, makes the class more interesting, develops their problem-solving skills (Timothy, 2015).

It is clear from the context and learners` needs, the most appropriate method to teach is Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) as its central point is to consider the language learning for mostly to obtain better communication skills in both spoken and written forms. Students can improve their communication skills much efficiently as “Communicative language teaching (CLT) is an approach to language teaching that emphasizes learning a language first and foremost for the purpose of communicating with others (Brown,2029). At present, we are living in technological century that`s way, connecting evdery field with technology is crucial especially education. Learning and teaching become beneficial when they are integrated with technology. Using technology turned into one of the students` interests. However, according to Hew, K. F. & Brush, T. (2007) there are some barriers toward the integration of technology into education: “insufficient resources, including inadequate access to technology and planning time; incomplete administrative support or school planning; perceptions that technology is inconsistent with the traditional culture of the subject area; negative teacher attitudes about technology; 5) lack of knowledge about and skills related to specific technologies, technology-supported pedagogy, and technology-related-classroom management; and 6) focus on using technology for computer-based testing rather than teaching and learning.”

There are two types of approaches to maintain the lesson based on teachers` and students` role in the lesson: teacher-centered and student-centered. If the students are more active than teachers during the lesson, it is student-centered lesson and it is considered to be so effective. The second one is teacher-centered and according to the rule of having a lesson based on this type: teachers are more active than students in the lesson. It is also considered to be effective but less than the previous one.

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